

Positive Personality Traits and Self-Efficacy as Correlates to Career Self-Management Among Public Secondary School Teachers

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative, non-experimental descriptive-correlational research aimed to ascertain the substantial impact of favorable personality qualities and teacher self-efficacy on career self-management on both an individual and collective level. Questionnaires made by the researcher on the three variables have been authenticated by the experts and then pilot tested for reliability test. These were administered to teachers in public schools within Davao City Division, using a stratified random sample of 228 teachers. Statistical Tools used are weighted mean, Pearson-r, and regression analysis in testing the hypotheses. The findings show: only outward and people orientation are at high levels, and the three indicators of positive personality traits, wit: positive self-image, commitment, and cultural identification, were at very high levels. The very high level of self-efficacy is due to both very high levels of academic and social stress and separation and discipline stress. Also, the high level of career self-management is due to the very high level of creating opportunities and seeking advice and the high level of enhancing one's visibility. Positive personality traits have a significant positive moderate correlation to career self-management, while teacher self-efficacy is significantly related to career self-management. Only 0.455 of career self-management will attribute to positive personality traits. Among the domains of positive personality traits, only the commitment indicator does not significantly influence career self-management. The indicators such as positive self-image, outward and people orientation, and cultural identification significantly influence career self-management. Positive personality traits significantly influence the career self-management of public secondary school teachers.

Keywords:- Positive Personality Traits, Teacher Self-Efficacy, Career Self-Management, Philippines.

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CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

➤ *Rationale*

Every year, the Department of Education, specifically in Division of Davao City, hires teachers from elementary up to senior high school to cater to the needs of every school that needs to fill in the teacher-student ratio of every classroom; moreover, in the secondary levels, the number of hired teachers increases due to the employment need of every school. However, despite the tenure of these teachers in their respective stations, it is noticeable that after years in public service, their acquainted career position upon assumption of duty could be more active. At ease, given such, as stated by Van der Want, Schellings, & Mommers (2018), some teachers need better career self-management skills due to factors affecting them. Because jobs are evolving from the traditional, "bounded," and driven by employment relations to being boundaryless and progressively self-directed by the employee (Arthur & Rosseau, 1996), the necessity of understanding career-self-management has been emphasized (King, 2004; Kossek et al., 1998). As a result, they tend to need more engagement and commitment to their career self-development.

Career self-development was considered one of the topics central to the Department of Education, especially for educators and others who are the frontline service providers of the teaching-learning process. The choice of possible work-related and academic choices drastically increased in society; teachers were anticipated in engaging life-long learning to cope broadly capable of the teaching-learning tasks assigned; further, since organizations have compressed and promotion-based professional beliefs are vanishing, teachers should generally be in control of their profession expansion. Afterward, teachers were suggested to dwell more on professional management, which refers to employees displaying proactivity in routing their profession through probing for a job (Runhaar et al., 2019). Furthermore, Lynch (2017) emphasized that there are several customs in moving the career ladder for classroom teachers. In a way, that is by transitioning into management. By returning to the institute and getting a degree in instruction management, educators can change to flattering assistant principals and head principals of a school.

It has been argued that there were contributing factors affecting the career self-development of employees, particularly personality traits, characteristics, goals, preferences, values, and self-efficacy were deemed to be included. It was pointed out in the study of de Jong, Wisse, Heesink, and Van der Zee (2019) that personality traits are associated with career self-development since it has significance in providing a more precise framework as an essential phenomenon in the academe. Thus, it has underlying importance since it acknowledges a person's trait alterations, especially preferred character, in explaining the progress of careers over time. Meanwhile, the study of Kaushal and Vashisht (2021) about self-efficacy and career self-management cited that these two are interdependent. From these studies, proactive personality and self-efficacy definitely and meaningfully influence career self-management behaviors after it was assessed via job mobility readiness and self-development seeking feedback. Thus, it is reasonable that practicing managers and organizations are keen on determining the character of employees who has an interest in career self-management behaviors, especially certainties underlying them.

Influential firms prioritize talent when choosing, fostering, and growing their employees. One-size-fits-all hiring practices by the government and school administration hinder effective and efficient staff management. The most excellent way to organize the teacher workforce for effectiveness and productivity is to manage individual talent and careers carefully. Professional and trade development practice too frequently fails to differentiate developmental paths for individual teachers. With this, self-management of employment and development is an essential skill that teachers must manifest. Although there were studies of personality traits in their different dimensions as predictors of career self-management on a prior and during basis, this research confirms the association between the two variables. In conclusion, it aimed in digging to explore the talks regarding the personality traits of teachers and the extent of their meaningful impact on career self-management, which supports recent comprehension towards personality motivation for achievement status in the educational area, such as in handling their boldness toward Arithmetic training.

➤ *Research Objective*

The primary objective of this research was to determine the significant influence of positive personality traits and self-efficacy on the career self-management of secondary public secondary school teachers in individual and aggregate capacities. Specifically, this pursued in answering these:

- *To Describe the Level of Positive Personality Traits in Terms of:*

- ✓ *Positive Self-Image,*
- ✓ *Commitment,*
- ✓ *Outward and People Orientation, and*
- ✓ *Culture Identification.*

- *To Ascertain the Level of Teacher Self-Efficacy in Terms of:*
 - ✓ *Academic and Social Stress, and*
 - ✓ *Separation and Discipline Stress.*
 - *To Measure the Level of Career Self-Management in Terms of:*
 - ✓ *Creating Opportunities,*
 - ✓ *Enhancing One's Visibility, and*
 - ✓ *Seeking Advice.*
 - *To establish the significance of the relationship between:*
 - ✓ *Positive Personality Traits and Career Self-Management, and*
 - ✓ *Teacher Self-Efficacy and Career Self-Management.*
 - ✓ *To Determine the Singular and Combined Influence of Positive Personality Traits and Teacher Self-Efficacy on Career Self-Management.*
- *Hypothesis*
The research study tested the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance:
- *There is no Significant Relationship between:*
 - ✓ *Positive Personality Traits and Career Self-Management, and*
 - ✓ *Teacher Self-Efficacy and Career Self-Management.*
 - *There is no Significant Influence between Positive Personality Traits and Teacher Self-Efficacy, Both in Individual and Aggregate Capacity.*

➤ *Review of Related Literature*

This part displays varied concepts, propositions, studies, and findings from related research and other resources on personality traits, self-efficacy, and career self-management. The first part discusses the personality traits along its indicators: positive self-image, commitment, outward and people orientation, and cultural identification. The second part discusses teacher self-efficacy and its indicators: academic and social stress and separation and discipline stress. The third part discusses career self-management and its hands: creating opportunities, enhancing visibility, and seeking advice. The last part discusses the relationship between personality traits and teacher self-efficacy in career self-management. Indicators of positive personality traits are positive self-image, commitment, outward and people orientation, and cultural identification (Singh, 2010). While self-efficacy indicators used are academic and social stress and separation and discipline stress (Heyne, Myerson, & Tonge, 2014). Lastly, the indicators used for career self-management are creating opportunities, enhancing one's visibility, and seeking advice (Runhaar, Bouwmans, & Vermeulen, 2019).

➤ *Positive Personality Traits*

Personality traits are a person's unique combination of different traits and qualities. It may be impacted by the development and evolution of a person's values, characteristics, interpersonal connections, and memories of significant life experiences, habits, and abilities. An individual's personality significantly influences their actions and choices (Chaudhari & Thakkar, 2019). Rezaei, Farahani, and Sejzehei (2019) also corroborate this notion by pointing out that more experienced teachers tend to take fewer risks and are more tolerant of uncertainty. Thus, their manifestation in growing professionally captures their direction in life, including values and attributes. Burch (2016) states that personality trait plays with the result of students' achievement coming from the behavior acted upon by the teacher towards them. In this case, it highlights the character wherein teachers' insights, attitudes, and outlook matter.

Moreover, their personality traits influence teachers' in-depth insights and outlooks. It affects how they approach professional development programs. He added that knowing and acknowledging personality trait differences can improve professional development outcomes. Thus, it has benefits in which the academe provides a deeper comprehension regarding the traits affecting their insights and outlook in the teaching-learning process. On the other hand, recent evidence argues the core factor associated with teacher performance. Thus, specifying personality traits (Buttner, Pijl, Bijstra, & van den Bosch, 2015). The results have practical ramifications for both instructional methods and teacher training programs.

This is stated in the study of Ali (2019) that the teachers' personality traits become versatile depending on the situation they are faced with. From an educational management perspective, information about teachers' personalities can justifiably create methods for effectively communicating and designate tasks suited for them. Moreover, Onuoha and Idemudia (2018) supported

that the role of high personality traits of teachers leads to the tendency to engage in negative work behavior, as it was shown in their study that male employees tend to obey more than females in a workplace setup.

In addition, Khalilzadeh and Khodi (2018) said that usually, personality and motivation are associated together in developing an effective technique for the learning process. It was stated that teachers have conscientious personality traits, which positively affect students' fundamental inspiration and knowledge. In addition, teachers' extraversion personality traits harmed students' inherent cause, accomplishment, and learning. It displays precisely which traits will get intensified or decrease students' motivation. Thus, the study results help teachers act accordingly within their profession. To support the research study's findings above, the Kennedy (2018) survey emphasized the association between teachers' personality traits and teachers' self-efficacy that impacted student learning. His quantitative and qualitative research results have shown that research participants seemed to the concept of personality traits, conscientiousness, agreeableness, and openness have an effect on student learning. Additionally, research participants also alleged that teacher self-efficacy had created a hole within students' innate self, especially in learning.

Furthermore, teachers' personality traits and verbal communication skills are noteworthy. According to Abdul & Ain's (2017) research, only openness among personality trait markers positively correlated with verbal communication. If students want to get the most out of their practical communication abilities, they must pay more attention to this quality.

In the field of business, the study by Mann and Rawat (2016) found that personality traits established a research-based fact emphasizing its influence on passion and emotional attachment to the brand. Aside from that, eroticism influenced affection and emotive attachment, while conscientiousness and openness impact experiencing, focusing on the attachment of connection to the brand. These, called brand personality dimensions of excitement, it covers that it has positively influenced consumer affection, connection, and passion for emotional attachment to the brand. Consequently, the consumer's emotional attachment towards the brand completely creates a bearing to satisfaction and loyalty. In conclusion, brand personality influences consumers' constancy toward the brand. The brand's social status ranking formulates a sense of being sincere, exciting, and competent, generating an affectionate, passionate, and connective emotional attachment with the brand.

Furthermore, Liring & Kartini (2016) found that demographic parameters like age, gender, education, and time frame holding created zero to no association with boldness. They used the well-known five personalities as a surrogate for personality traits. According to other findings, conscientiousness and overconfidence are positively correlated, whereas extraversion, agreeableness, neuroticism, and openness to new experiences are not.

The abovementioned shows the relevance of personality traits not just in the field of education but in other disciplines. The findings and additional concepts discussed are of great significance to provide a more precise framework of personality traits as an essential phenomenon in the academe.

Positive Self-image. Positive self-image affects people's view of themselves, their interaction with others, then their feelings about their surroundings. As a result, it affects many people's life. Positivity about oneself can enhance the wellbeing of oneself physically, mentally, socially, emotionally, and spiritually. On the other hand, having a negative view of ourselves can impact our behavior and general pleasure (Lynch, 2020).

This is supported by the study of Mehrkish & Grant (2021), revealing that the managers' positive self-image significantly contributes to their attitude. Moreover, it implies that a positive self-image strongly impacts their performance in their designated workstation.

Commitment. The profession of teaching demands not less than but more than commitment. Educators, by heart, are committed to their students as wellbeing and the profession perse in general. These counts follow the constitutional and ethical laws and ordinances and embrace the full requirements of the guiding principles within the academe. As pointed out, commitment is someone who is willing to extend a hand and exert an extra mile in the greater glory of their job. Thus, concluding that they normalized it within their point of view because active participation in the profession means growing for them. Thus, committed individuals are seen to be lifelong learners in the teaching profession (Cox, 2017). Nevertheless, educators who are statistically proven to have moderately low levels of commitment frequently end up resigning from their job because of certain factors which they find gruesome to be resolved (Shirbagi, 2007). Further, the teachers' commitment dug a hole of hope within their daily activities in school. Therefore, it becomes a consideration in a broader aspect of orientation towards motivation within each professional since it displays professional knowledge and feature of quality.

Commitment is generally defined as an individual attitude that characterizes the relationship between two parties. Beyond this, commitment is considered a multifaceted construct, which includes three components (affective, normative, and calculative). These three commitment components can be distillate into a variety of concentrations like occupation, organization, supervisor, and workgroup (Webs et al., 2016).

Outward and People Orientation. In outward and people orientation, this refers to a person's self-confidence. This includes being outgoing and gregarious in social situations with an enthusiastic approach, showing self-esteem, and having the confidence to lead others (Singh & Jha, 2010). They also added that it depicts exertion and willpower, approachability, family orientation, social welfare, manners to the elderly, and belief in God. To specify more, it added attachment to others, tradition and respect for country, restraint, affection, sanguinity, devotion, and triumph. This study was supported by Gartzia & Baniandres (2016), which organizes this outward and people orientation aspect as related to two primary dimensions: people orientation and task orientation. Thus, it is stipulated that this displays how people's directions are practical in task-related managerial activities.

Cultural Identification. In culture identification, it is pointed out by Singh & Jha (2010) that it refers to the orientation toward one's culture and country. This comprises direction toward an individual's cultural, national, traditional, and acceptance of these. Further, as Chen 2014 added in cultural identity, an individual has identification with, or a feeling of belonging to, or identification with, a specific cluster based on social characteristics such as race, nationality, ethnicity, religion, and gender. Moreover, cultural identity is built together and sustained through allocating collective knowledge such as language, traditions, aesthetics, heritage, customs, and norms. To support these studies, Wan (2015) mentioned that intersubjective cultural illustration offers an expressive basis for individuals to develop uniqueness with the culture. Precisely, the more an individual's values are aligned with values intersubjective represented to be necessary, the closer an individual is to a culture, the more closely they would identify with that culture. Future studies on cultural identity formation, particularly in multicultural environments, will need to consider how intersubjective representation functions in cultural identification.

➤ *Teacher Self-Efficacy*

The social cognition principle develops the concept of self-efficacy (Bandura 2006 in Shu 2022). He added that this is a multidimensional concept and is the more core human agency mechanism, for instance, the capability to affect one's functioning and living conditions purposefully. As added by Van Acker et al. (2013) in Shu (2022), self-efficacy is similar to the ability of individuals to act. It explains that performance may be affected accordingly to the person's behavior, also, the context in which it occurs.

In addition, the cognitive theory of behavior changes emphasizes the part of cognition in the attainment and guideline of behavior, which includes the person's self-efficacy. Furthermore, it was discussed that there are expectations within personal efficacy because it can affect a particular coping behavior that is initiated. Thus, it includes effort and persistence in difficulties (Bandura, 1997 in Heyne, Myerson, & Tonge, 2014). It becomes factual through proven research that teacher self-efficacy positively impacts a variety of teaching and learning aspects. Most of the teachers characterize that they are more capable of instructional strategies since they have a high level of classroom management and student engagement.

Second, the tenure of a teacher in teaching attached to the training courses finished negatively shows significance in teachers' self-efficacy beliefs (Al-Shukri, 2016).

Apparently, teachers restructure policies, which in the latter part, makes them accountable for the possible increase of their feeling of exhaustion and possibly lesser planes of teacher self-efficacy. As revealed, connections between exhaustion and self-efficacy were steady compared to other studies. In contrast, zero to small correlations has been found within educators' attitudes about the improvement responsibility procedures of school grades and performance pay and exhaustion. Multiple regression models cast off in assessing the likelihood of exhaustion within teacher self-efficacy and teachers' boldness regarding the improvement procedures caused by few noteworthy analysts from the teacher boldness subscales. Probable implications are discoursed pertinent to academical leadership, teacher turnover, then inhibited know-how (Folk, 2015 in Lanza, 2020).

Moreover, the Dobbins (2016) study claimed no substantial relations were associated with teacher self-efficacy and grit as compared to student outcomes (student growth percentiles). However, it suggests an affiliation between self-efficacy and grit, as proposed that building self-efficacy is equivalent to enhanced teacher grit.

Traditionally, the role of teachers must help all students achieve academic success in a safe and nurturing learning environment. However, their role has become increasingly more challenging and less rewarding. One major contributing factor is the rise of disruptive behavior in the classroom. Upon analyzing the data of this study, there was an exposition showing a significant correlation between the self-perceptions of elementary teachers and their ability to control the unsettling behavior of students, especially those who have concerns with socialization disruptive behavior of students who lack social competence. Results further revealed that teachers' self-efficacy predicts student performance on state tests. The implications of producing high-performing, socially competent students include admin and school-related psychotherapists working collaboratively in fostering higher self-efficacy among educators (Jackson, 2015).

As teachers discern about self-efficacy, it equates the characteristics they practice. Limited research links teachers' insights into self-efficacy and practices shown in the classroom, especially in instructional techniques. There were significant discrepancies between teachers' self-reported self-efficacy and observers' evaluations. There were tackling topics implying the use of for future research, professional growth, and school psychology practice (Poulou et al., 2019).

In the study of Ali & Bagheri (2018), it was stated that the influence of self-efficacy, school context, and self-esteem showed that self-efficacy has a significant direct negative effect on depersonalization and reduced personal accomplishment. Also, school context significantly affected emotive tiredness, reification, and abridged own achievement. Thus, self-esteem had a direct outcome in the abovementioned school context.

Academic and social stress. Academic and social stress as self-efficacy indicators has various internal and external deliberations paving the way to creating a portion in the academe. To thoroughly explain it, the changes arising at an individual and societal level create susceptible issues related to academic stress. Therefore, the academic pressure comprising its causes needs to be determined so that effective intervention may be applied. The development of helpful counseling modules and intervention methods by school psychologists and counselors to assist kids in reducing stress would be made easier with an understanding of the origins of stress (Reddy et al., 2018). Additionally, academic and social stress appears to display the person's principles about their skill in coping situations that elicit a behavioral response which could be in the form of academic concerns, just as doing school works and paper works, and social status that entails answering questions or teasing, presenting self in a group, or forthcoming towards teachers (Van Acker et al, 2013 in Shu 2022). It was found in the study that there are worries that the respondents came across, especially in answering peers' questions whenever they are away from school. Thus, it simply reveals that teachers have difficulty handling peers' questions.

Further studies show that academic and social stress is a condition of mental pressure for individuals battling social and environmental health issues, which cause many ailments. As elaborated, during young age, it is expected to be the elite in society since this is the critical period because youth face many life changes. They should manage skillfully their stresses to live healthily once they know they have entered the academe's field. A youngster entering adolescence must adjust to new lifestyle and surroundings and become accustomed to various new people, situations, and objects. They are under a great deal of life stress. Therefore, it's crucial to comprehend the causes of stress and their coping mechanisms (Bhargava & Trevidi, 2018).

Academic and social stress is a noted phenomenon in the field; however, there needs to be more agreement among various professional groups on how to approach it. According to a review of international studies, teacher academic and social stress is a natural phenomenon, and high levels are consistently linked to various root causes, such as intrinsic motivation to teach, personal vulnerability, and systemic influences (Nyambongi, 2013). Moreover, the study of Shamar and Shakir (2017) emphasized that academic and social stress has a detrimental impact on teachers' health. It also harms their work performance. Stress affects work satisfaction and overall happiness. Cumulative pressure is recognized as a work-related danger. Besides, educators exposed to non-stop stress affect their capacity to respond effectively to classroom concerns since they are already physically and mentally struggling with their health. When a teacher himself is in a stressed or distressed state, then how will his students remain stress-free?

Academic and social stress levels have also been associated with adverse health outcomes. Mindfulness-based stress management skills could help employees handle stress manageably since eliminating stressors is impossible. It would then train them to become optimistic and resilient to their daily stresses. (Kennedy et al., 2018). It is also a meaningful contribution that understanding current academic and social stress within a primary education context.

Separation and discipline stress. Separation and discipline stress discuss people's beliefs about the coping mechanism of people when faced with a challenging situation. Elaboratively, it threatens security due to the nonappearance of loved ones or grown-ups, especially when separated for any duration of the day. The emotional challenge could also be intimidating circumstances, with grown-ups focusing on being penalized or conference by authorities (Heyne et al., 2014). The study revealed that participants have high levels of separation and discipline stress, which suggests a lower risk of separation anxiety and fear of retribution.

Further discussion was explained by Lewis (1999), stating that separation and discipline stress refers to how teachers efficiently manage the classroom. One of the most essential tasks of being a teacher is regulating peace and order in school. Some may face problems in selecting methods of classroom management because they want to apply theory-based learning they have acquired while swiftly establishing and keeping order in the classroom. And by such, they mostly show worries, self-blame, strain, wishful thinking, and keeping to oneself. Teachers who invest too much emotion claim to have an increased inclination to stress-related illness. These points need professional development programs to help teachers reflect on various more effective coping mechanisms and effectively share power with students.

The subject of discipline often needs to be clarified with classroom management. Although connected, discipline and classroom management are two entirely separate issues. They are concerned with how things are carried out in the classroom. It requires structure, rules, and routines that are almost ceremonial. Classroom management is improved when systems are presented to students; they practice them, and if necessary, they are frequently reinforced by practicing again. Instruction becomes effective when techniques are mastered, implemented, and supported. This is the cornerstone of effective classroom management and the teacher's primary duty.

Discipline, in contrast to classroom management, is the student's duty. Correct behavior is what discipline is all about. Although the teacher's responsible for keeping the classroom in a learning-friendly environment, each individual is also accountable for their behavior (Marshall, 2005). On a related point, some teachers were still exhausted due to discipline and behavior problems. Kids' disruptive behavior that results in suspensions might be a knock-on consequence of teacher stress on the kids. Students in their classrooms are more likely to face suspension or disciplinary action from school officials when teachers are under tremendous pressure and emotional exhaustion (Consiglio-Missouri, 2020).

➤ *Career Self-Management*

Teachers can tremendously benefit from learning about and exercising self-management since teaching is demanding. Sadly, teachers may be concerned that self-care could result in self-absorption. The extent to which one consistently collects data and makes strategies in career problem-solving and decision-making has been described as career self-management. According to Marcinek's (2015) research, career self-management focuses on instructors' ability to assess their goals and capabilities. Moreover, they are expected to know the laid-open opportunities and their quick handful grasp for suitability which should be admired by their supervisors. They added that it could be a source of the competencies and ambitions of the teacher.

According to studies, people seek and gather knowledge about their jobs to evaluate their competency and work chances and make wise professional selections. A person should juggle their knowledge with their personal strengths and weakness, then jump to making career decisions. The efficiency of the overall career management process depends on the individual seeking out information about their career. Career self-management is the combination of the employer-employee responsibility in nurturing the latter. Organizational career management entails using rules and procedures to improve employees' career performance. Individual career management, or career self-management, meanwhile, refers to the individual efforts made by employees to progress their careers Kaushal and Vashisht (2021).

Moreover, there is a need for a better understanding of career self-management. It was claimed that people utilize high manifestations of career self-managing behavior as adaptive responses to career development tasks. Managing one's job well can increase one's sense of control over it and increase work fulfillment, but it can also be linked to unfavorable results and disturbance (King, 2014). Teachers with a high level of career self-management empower others to reach the greater peak and encourage them to move mountains for their professional ownership of development. It gives sense to both the organization and its people, and it specifies the precise actions people and organizations need to do to make the idea work. Most teachers are likely to take responsibility for themselves if there is sound organizational support. However, with the right practical initiatives, the process can energize them. However, if performance levels at work are to be improved from competence to excellence in managing their careers, businesses must focus much more intently on understanding people as individuals (Stickland, 2018).

Maximizing one's productivity is permitted within career self-management skills. It also improves job performance and develops professional objectives. Thus, one of the ways to boost employability is to develop abilities in self-management since students have shown that it is a better way to handle and manage the professional path. Self-management skills are organization, objective, prioritizing strategy, enthusiasm, stress reduction, and accountability (Indeed Editorial Team, 2020).

The concerned individual controls career self-management, including specific strategies and information for future career decision-making and problem-solving. They manifest a high level of career self-management, including making progress on current conditions within the place of work, then later equip themselves for possible changes. Career self-management and organizational career management may promote each other. Thus. It is enclosed of unceasing improvement on the current conditions (Jacowski, 2021).

Three abilities that everyone should master are the cornerstones of self-management: acquiring time and commitment management skills, developing the desire and capacity to study unknowns in one's work, and creating and maintaining a personal network. With those skills, one will be successful in his career (Suess, 2015). 21st century learning asks for self-management skills. It was found that mastering self-management skills include self-assessment, setting a goal, managing time, and regulating the self. Generally, it formulates the usefulness of self-management skills (Gerhardt, 2017).

Talking about career self-management will touch on the idea of counseling in education. Staiculescu, Lacatus, and Nastase (2015) wrote that concepts used to describe career counseling services have particular meanings in the counseling literature. Career lifelong counseling means the services and activities that help people, regardless of age or life stage, to make choices regarding their education, training, or jobs and effectively manage their careers. Career counseling refers to development in the academe and knowledge and skills people need to manage their education and professional path effectively. The process of orientation and training towards subjects, specializations, and domains according to their personalities defines it. Professional exercise and analysis are any specialized activity in which anyone may benefit regarding a career prime, career growth, professional re-training, employability increase, ways to maintain or change a job, or any other (Yogalakshmi & Suganthi, 2020). The above-related concepts from different authors provide a framework regarding career self-management to understand the variable further. The related ideas serve as bases for more precise points in grasping how career self-management has been used in research and academia.

Creating Opportunities as the first indicator is considered when a person develops skills he determines desirable career goals. This could be seen when teachers explicitly inquire about available budgets for expert growth and use them in specific courses (Marcinek, 2015). They also pointed out that this indicator of successful career self-management can be seen in teachers who open the door to initiating activities on themes commonly ignored by others. Thus, it claims that teachers are observed to open prospects for other potential development or improvement.

In addition, expert knowledge becomes operative when educators can personalize the experience and communicate authentically among other professionals with the same interest. These academic learning chances should be preserved as something other than mere tests. Expert expansion should reflect the distinctive strands of a teacher's professional career. We shouldn't dread it; instead, we should want it and seek it out. Educators often have a distinctive yearning to learn and grow professionally. The desire to be a lifelong learner and to set an example for our pupils by modeling this behavior is the driving principle and philosophy that advances education (Marcinek, 2015).

The consensus is that few influence learning and teaching. It was suggested that the cultural-historical action theory discusses comprehending the advantages of having researchers in the school for both instructors and students. It was stated the importance of utilizing the affordances that develop with the presence of researchers in educational settings from the insights of cultural-historical activity theory and the concept of expanded knowledge. It was suggested in the conclusion that participants should use the chances for teaching and learning that exist when scholars are present to increase the "impact" of research, at least locally (Maheux & Roth, 2013).

In terms of enhancing one's visibility, the second indicator explains that teachers effectively communicate with their supervisor to attain certain goals, like implementing a new pedagogical method. They elaborated on this by specifying an example wherein a teacher could make way professional in notifying one's accomplishment to the supervisor. They added that openness toward the supervisor could enhance one's visibility. It includes sharing one's goal or dream.

In addition, Tuitt (2010) developed an in-depth comprehension as his research was conducted through a qualitative design focusing on the perceived improved visibility within their learning environment. The result revealed that a participant's experience made him feel a sense of pressure and, at the same time, validated when he was recognized or noticed by his superior. Moreover, it was also seen in the result of the study, in general, that it develops engagement in teachers' senses because it develops their ideas without compromising their dignity and humanity. Thus, it brings success and a sense of accomplishment towards the work they have had.

Seeking Advice. As explained in Rijt, Boscche, Van De Wiel, & Maeyer's (2013) study, asking for advice is an essential step to rooting out problems and future learning in organizations. Teachers are more likely to seek help from higher-profile individuals and much lesser than lower-status individuals. This is due to the valuable insights acquired mostly by higher-status individuals, especially in approaching constructively their given advice.

Moreover, the study of Berebitsky and Andrews-Larson (2017) explained that instructors' interactions with superiors or co-workers significantly affected how well they teach and how well their students learn. Teachers who seek advice from peers knowledgeable about academics and professionalism have demonstrated evolution in their classroom instructional practice. Mainly, teachers with social network access to subject-specific instructional expertise are likelier to display and maintain evidence of instructional improvement. Aside from discovering the patterns of teachers in advice-seeking, there were few studies have who have examined this predictable cycle of seeking advice from their superiors or other experts in schools undergoing systematic instructional reform.

In addition, Today's school administrators must juggle an overwhelming number of tasks and commitments in addition to what seems like endless state and federal obligations. The function of instructional leadership consequently receives less attention than it ought to. The most crucial position for an administrator to play is as an instructional leader since it gives them the most chance to have an influence. Administrators must assist instructors in matching learning experiences with content and skill objectives in their capacity as instructional leaders. To improve their visibility, they must mentor teachers to design learning activities that maximize student accomplishment (Matthew, 2019).

It is often claimed that the profession of teaching is the one that gives rise to all others. Consequently, we must understand how to do it properly. In particular, how they identify one other's areas of competence and whether they are prone to turn to the most knowledgeable for guidance and assistance are likely to have a significant role in how teachers learn from one another (Busch, 2018).

➤ *Correlation between Measures*

A person's personality dramatically influences how they act in different circumstances. The evolution of careers has been connected to several aspects of nature. It is possible that an individual's profession is highly associated with the personality trait they manifest. Personality affects professional choices such as profession selection, early career socialization, job performance, career happiness, and career changes (Boudreau et al., 2011).

As added, personality significantly influences motivation for choosy attitudes, principles, and character differences. Upon being joined to a set of groups, their stable traits consequently affect their behavior and performance. Additionally, when hiring individuals, businesses anticipate possessing particular knowledge, skills, abilities, personalities, and beliefs. As empirical evidence confirmed, personality traits positively correlate with choosing a teaching career path as a profession. Individuals bring some differences to work (Tomsik & Gatial, 2018). Moreover, personality influences individuals' essential choices, including the option of a partner and education. And career. Connectedly, these are people's considerations in picking a profession: capability and ability to work by trade and tenure of working (Alkheilil, 2016). He added that having a job boosts a person's self-identity in the society. An acquired career could rank up one's self-esteem and, thus, stretches belongingness with the community they are dwelled at. Thus, his study showed that personality influences the career management of every individual due to the person's driving force.

The proposition study by Gunkel, Schlaegel, Langella, & Peluchette, 2010 in Lin, Luan, Zhao, et al. (2022) testifies that personality traits and career self-management have emerged as significantly related. It is found that these are the associations of an individual's personality traits: nationality, career beliefs, performance variables, and occupation.

Additionally, this study is supported by Runhaar, Bouwmans, & Vermeulen (2019) by revealing that scholarly research studies are illuminating that there is an increase of attribution on the accountability of handling one's career to teachers' personality traits. Hence, teachers are seen to be pilots of their own careers. Navigating one's job requires events that permit educators to evaluate their aptitudes and then competencies because of occupation chances in their institutions, and within these actions, educators deem to realize their ambition to target. Thus, it will enable them to manage careers according to their pacing. Contrary to these studies, it was revealed that personality does not predict all the career self-management of individuals (Kemboi, R.J.K., Kindiki, N., Misigo, N., 2016).

Moreover, it shows that different personality traits relate to various career self-management. As this finding was revealed, they concluded that this should be investigated further. They elaborated that this needs to be more consistent among other research regarding these variables. Thus, it suggests a more integrative understanding of the two variables in future studies. In other studies, it was shown that a relationship between personality and career management was visible as they have adopted Holland's theory. Countless times, it was conducted in other countries, but the current research focused on the Kenyan context, suggesting that a deepened and widened investigation regarding the potential of personality types towards choices in career may be ventured (Kemboi et al., 2016).

While there are no or limited studies on personality traits and career self-management, the above-related literature can be used as a ground for the framework that will provide clear points regarding how personality can be an attribute of career management. Moreover, the above-related concepts from different sources and literature reviews are the blueprints for exploring the significant influence of personality traits on career self-management.

In the correlation between teacher self-efficacy and career self-management, the study of Reddan (2015) begins to develop a course wherein it tests teachers' self-efficacy in making decisions and developing their careers. The system commenced with a work experience placement. As the plan got along, workshops related to career self-management awakened their knowledge within their self-awareness, opportunity awareness, and aspirations. After the course, they were tested through a survey questionnaire about self-efficacy and career self-management as to self-appraisal, occupational information, goal selection, planning, and problem-solving. As a result, it was revealed that teachers' perceived awareness of their strengths and weaknesses in their self-efficacy and career self-management. Thus, as the effects were assessed on how they were related, it was evident that these two have a significant relationship. As it implies that the teachers know their strengths and weakness, they have a broader understanding of attaining career goals and plans. An additional study shows that based on Parson's Trait and Factory theory, factors affect an individual in career management.

These are the realization of yourself accurately or self-awareness, understanding the work environment and requirements or the occupational information, and matching yourself with the workload or self-efficacy (Sun, 2019). The result found that teachers' career management is highly related to matching awareness within their load or self-efficacy. It concludes that teachers need self-efficacy to have the confidence to make appropriate decisions for their career self-management.

Moreover, another study supported previous findings, which revealed that self-efficacy and career self-management are significantly correlated, implying that these two variables have a significant relationship (Alisic & Wiese, 2020). Their study found that decreasing career insecurity increases self-efficacy, enhancing career-self management. They added that this anchored

the motivational theory of life-span development and the social self-regulation theory. Moreover, in their further elaboration, they have explained that based on their study's result, teachers built the responsibility of managing their careers as they have a high level of self-efficacy. Thus, it concludes that the more efficient teachers are, the more they can work themselves.

In addition to these studies, Lee, Jung, Baek, and Lee's (2022) research in South Korea found that emotions and self-confidence are crucial in career decision-making and that difficulties experienced strongly correlate with career self-efficacy. They emphasized that the higher a person's career self-efficacy behavior, the higher the career management and decision-making he will commit. They also added that this finding implies that when a person has a higher career self-efficacy, they are more frequently engaged in career preparation behavior or self-management. Moreover, the results mean that self-efficacy is related to career preparation behavior, specifying that career self-efficacy directly affects it.

The field of, and just recently, this set of variables was tested in engineering. The study showed that self-efficacy has a significant impact and relation to career self-management (Makki et al., 2023). The Malaysian University surveyed engineers who showed skillfulness in their field in contribution to their career growth decision-making. They are taken as participants as they are seen to be typically having difficulty focusing on their career path due to their inability to make decisions despite their abilities and skills developed confidently. The study findings found that when a person is work ready, it will reflect on their self-efficacy, thus showing an elevation of their career exploration management substitutes. Moreover, it was concluded that a person's resilience could strongly affect his or her decision-making when talking about exploration management.

In the study of Kaushal and Vashisht (2021), they tested a model of self-efficacy and career self-management using the moderating effect, which is the proactive personality. They utilized hierarchical multiple regression in testing the theoretical model that itemized the association among the three variables. It was suggested that the moderating effect positively and significantly influenced career self-management. The ramifications of the findings in terms of theory and practice are examined. The study results could be used by practicing managers and organizations to determine employees' engagement in career self-management behaviors and other related contexts in which such occurrence of behavior.

Rahim, Jafar, and Arsad (2021) said that choosing a career or sector of employment is one of the few decisions that significantly impact people's lives. In addition to the fact that most individuals spend a lot more time working than doing anything else (other than sleeping, choosing a career significantly impacts lifestyle, and work-life balance is closely linked to mental and physical health. Although there is a relative neglect of issues in career or work within the psychological field, researchers have been studying career choice and work adjustment, which leads to the development of theoretical models within talks of career choice.

Lent, Ireland, Penn, Morris, and Sappington (2017) also evaluated the prime empirical foundations of self-efficacy and consequence prospects concerning professional investigation and policymaking actions. Some of these sources were own knack, spoken coaxing, displaced knowledge, and affect (both good and bad) experienced during job inquiry and supervisory. The findings on the vital link between self-efficacy and career self-management are evaluated in light of the social cognitive career theory, and its implications for future study and practice are examined.

Individuals make choices and decisions when choosing their profession and be in their field of work. In addition, a position suitable to someone's trait was proven to have a significant opportunity to satisfy their psychological needs. Moreover, it was claimed that personality trait is an essential factor affecting career management, choices, and decisions (Crant, 2006; Ustuner, 2017). However, exploring the individual's self-efficacy, personality traits, and career management was recommended, as one may be a mediating variable (Ebstrup et al., 2011; Ustuner, 2017). Thus, as further exploration was done by Ustuner (2017) conceptualizing the relationship between personality traits, teacher self-efficacy belief, and career management, it was discovered that instructors' self-efficacy and personality attributes had a favorable impact on career management. It was then concluded that self-efficacy and personality trait has a role with a solid relation to teachers' career management.

It is essential to comprehend what factors affect teachers' capacity to successfully handle duties, commitments, and difficulties associated with career self-management. Thus, the relationship between teachers' personality traits or values and self-efficacy towards their motivation in giving attention to their career management was purposively explored (Sousa et al., 2012; Barni et al., 2019). In the findings, it was revealed that teachers' traits or values and teachers' self-efficacy were shown to be significant predictors of their efficiency in managing careers. It was evident that teachers who recognized their ability to handle their tasks and obligations effectively and their manifestation of character worked their jobs as part of their interest; thus, they concluded that these are significant factors in fostering career management.

The above-cited reviews on related literature and studies reinforce the understanding of the concepts explored. With the exploration of each variable commencing from positive personality traits, self-efficacy, and career self-management, each indicator is understood as how other researchers used them in different contexts. The relative association between the variables was also explored, and these findings were used as a framework for establishing this study.

➤ *Theoretical Framework*

This study is primarily attached by the Cognitive Career Theory Model of Career Self-Management, wherein individuals direct their career development and navigate career transitions under varying cognitive, personal, and contextual influences. The normative transfer from learned knowledge to the workplace has become more difficult due to shifting work settings and unstable economic situations, necessitating the development of adaptable skills and resiliency in the face of difficulty. In light of these facts, the CSM model strongly emphasizes the ideas of adaptive professional behaviors and personal agency. It highlights how these concepts can support people in taking control of their career growth and managing job changes (Wendling & Sagas, 2020). Moreover, this is anchored in the proposition of the study testifying that personality and career self-management are connected as the latter was found to be associated in a broader range within an individual's career belief and performance variables, irrespective of occupation and nationality. Emphasizing that traits are seen to be influential and a factor in an individual's decisions within career self-management (Gunkel et al., 2010; Lin et al., et al. (2022).

Further, as John Holland from Holland Codes concisely explained, suitable jobs for every individual within their personality create a happier and more productive working environment. (Whiteberry, 2016). Contemporary career literature, named 'new career,' points out that there is satisfaction among people who have successfully managed their careers as they reach more significant goals through their initiative to adjust dynamically within the environment they have dwelled in (Jung & Takeuchi, 2018). Thus, A recent study has reinforced this proposition as scholars have seen the increasing attribute of the obligation of handling an employee's career. However, the latter are still seen as the prime factor in navigating their career paths. Course-plotting self-career involves activities that permit an individual to evaluate their aptitude and proficiencies because of career breakthroughs at their schools and the activities which teachers may utilize in reaching their goals (Runhaar et al., 2019).

Another theory incorporates this study as Parson's Trait and Factory Theory in 1909 by Frank Parsons suggests emphasizing the person and environment fit ideas. This theory proposes that career self-management may be predicted based on an individual's characteristics, especially aptitudes, achievements, interests, and self-efficacy. He elaborated that there are identifications in the career self-management, and these are people's: clear understanding of their skills, abilities, limitations, resources, effectiveness, and other qualities; determined knowledge and success conditions, its chances, reward, and anticipation towards variety of work field; and, philosophizing on the relationship of facts. These elements enumerated by Parson significantly relate to an individual's self-efficacy and career self-management. Moreover, the recent proposition is strikingly consistent, revealing that as individuals realize their accuracy or self-awareness in understanding the environment and requirement or the occupational information to match their workload, they are more likely to push through within their career self-management (Sun, 2019).

Lastly, this is anchored on the Career Roles Model propositioned by Hoekstra (2011), as cited by de Jong, Wisse, Heesink, and van der Zee (2019), that career development is labeled through its communicating development in both interior profession distinctiveness formation and the development of exterior profession distinctiveness significance. This concept specifies that it is not solely jobs but career roles related to an individual's success and satisfaction. It was elaborated that a career holds an individual's life journey and identity. Primarily, it comes first within their motives which underlie commitment, long-term goals, values, and personality traits. Also, in the dimensions described by the theory, career development may be affected by two things: an individual's career motives which are characterized by their personality, values, and interests, and the individual's career role and performance, which are related to the work performance, job satisfaction, career satisfaction, abilities, skills, effectiveness, and competence – and these can be attributed based on a personal basis or relevant others such as peers. Thus, it was patently consistent that the recent proposition shows relevance with the theory beforementioned stating that the relations between teachers' personality traits or values and self-efficacy towards their motivation in giving attention to their career management were revealed to be essential predictors in testing the efficiency of managing their careers since teachers, who already recognized their ability in handling their tasks and obligations effectively together with their manifestation of characters containing their careers then, were part of their interest; and thus, being concluded that these are significant factors in fostering career management.

These abovementioned theories, concepts, and propositions are of great help in establishing points of reference that provide frameworks for this study regarding how personality traits act as determinants of the career self-management of teachers.

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework, wherein the independent variables are personality traits and teacher self-efficacy. For positive personality traits, the indicators are positive self-image, commitment, outward and people orientation, and cultural identification. In contrast, for teacher self-efficacy, the hands are academic and social stress and separation and discipline stress. The dependent variable is career self-management with these indicators: creating opportunities, enhancing visibility, and seeking advice.

Personality trait refers to the characteristics manifested by the teachers regarding their personalities. This is defined through positive self-image, commitment, outward and people orientation, and cultural identification. Positive self-image refers to the direction towards preserving a positive self-image that embraces an optimistic outlook in life, building rapport and relationships within the self positively, and seeing the self as supple, emotionally intelligent, reasonable, spiritual, truthful, and independent.

Commitment refers to devotion of self to the perspective and objectives and association towards others. Predisposition to initiate movements toward one's life and respond to others can be counted as commitment. It contains facets of goal setting, pliability, learning new things, self-reliance, uniqueness, gratefulness, bigheartedness, and trustworthiness. Outward and people orientation refers to the assurance of empathizing with themselves, which includes the ability to be outward-bound and extroverted in social situations, an enthusiastic approach, self-esteem, and the confidence to lead others. Cultural identification refers to the knowledge of a person of customs and traditions in another nation or denomination. It includes a course toward one's traditions, nationalism, and open-mindedness toward others (Singh, 2010).

Teachers who believe they can successfully manage their professional activity's tasks, responsibilities, and obstacles have high teacher self-efficacy. It significantly impacts high-ordered thinking academic outcomes (such as student progress and motivation) and wellbeing in the workplace. Its indicators are educational and social stress and separation and discipline stress. Academic and social stress refers to the cheerful disposition manifested by teachers in handling academic-related and social-related stress at work. In contrast, separation and discipline stress refers to how teachers manage separation and discipline-related factors in their work (Heyne et al., 2014).

Career self-management refers to how teachers manage their careers for improvement and for addressing needs and difficulties. This is defined as creating opportunities, enhancing visibility, and seeking advice. Creating opportunities refers to how teachers subject themselves to managing the enhancement of their careers. Improving one's visibility refers to the activity initiated by the teachers to be recognized for their work. Seeking advice relates to teachers' initiative to solicit others' ideas on managing their careers (Runhaar et al., 2019).

Within Figure 1, the flow of the research from personality traits and teacher self-efficacy shows wherein they are significantly influencing the career self-management of public secondary school teachers.

Fig 1 The Schematic Diagram Showing the Variables of the Study

➤ *Significance of the Study*

This study investigates the relationship between positive personality traits and career self-management, teacher self-efficacy, and career self-management; it also determines the influence of positive personality traits and teacher self-efficacy on career management in a singular and combined form. The results may be valuable in planning educational and indicative programs to consider teacher self-efficacy with their commensurate personality traits, as these play a significant role in academic fields.

Further, the significance of the study is more likely related to the following: teachers, school administrators, and future researchers. The teachers could use this as an avenue for awareness of their positive personality traits and self-efficacy in their career self-management.

Additionally, school administrators could use this to determine the teachers' goals and orientation within their career self-management relating to their positive personality traits and self-efficacy. It will help them discover the precise direction of dreams among teachers. It will also enable them to improve institutional programs initiated by them to address teachers' personality traits and career self-management. Also, this would allow teachers to engage in worth-reflecting activities evaluating their personality traits and career self-management and enhance these variables through schemes. By understanding the personality traits of professionals and their career self-management skills, the education sector can support the demands of future job skills.

Future researchers may explore other variables of various contexts to respond to problems of social and economic divides created by the pandemic. Moreover, the social value of this study is relevant to the academe, as academics have highlighted the exigency of comprehending career self-management since, over time, there is a changing nature of career which is driven by the role of self-efficacy and personality traits (Skrikanth, 2012). Emphasizing that good management skills maximize productivity, increase working performance, and effective professional goal achievement follow. Additionally, it might make a person more employable and help them manage career trajectories better (Runhaar, P., Bouwans, & Vermeulen 2019).

➤ *Definition of Terms*

In establishing a common edge of reference, these are the terms operationally used within the study:

• *Personality Traits.*

It refers to the characteristics manifested by the teachers regarding their personalities. This is defined through positive self-image, commitment, outward and people orientation, and cultural identification.

• *Self-Efficacy.*

This refers to the belief in their skills in managing effectively obligations and tasks and work-related challenges for their professional growth. This is defined through teacher positivity and instructional practices.

• *Career Self-Management.*

This refers to how teachers manage their careers for improvement and for addressing needs and difficulties. This is defined as creating opportunities, enhancing visibility, and seeking advice.

CHAPTER TWO METHOD

The chapter discusses the research design, locale, population and sample, instrument, data collection, and statistical tools.

➤ *Research Design*

The research employed quantitative non-experimental research. Specifically, this study employed descriptive-correlational analysis in which Curtis, Comiskey, and Dempsey (2016) describe how correlation research aims to find connections between identical variables in two or more populations or between the same variables in the same population. Additionally, they added that it is an essential part of a research study since comprehending the relations and associations among phenomena maintains to be the remaining incentive for investigations.

Moreover, this study employs quantitative because the data collected are numerical, and the treatment commenced with tallying and statistical computation. Furthermore, the researcher intends to use this research design since it gathers the teachers' positive personality traits and self-efficacy in their career self-management. The collected data of the independent variables: positive personality traits and self-efficacy, were correlated to the dependent variable: career self-management. By doing this, it can be accurately analyzed after administering and retrieving the survey questionnaire set by the researcher. Through this process, the researcher purposely uses these data to investigate the significant influence of personality traits and self-efficacy on the career self-management of public secondary school teachers. By this, the understanding of these phenomena was much more in-depth and accurate.

➤ *Research Locale*

The study was directed in Davao Region, Region XI, Philippines secondary schools. More specifically, the location of the schools where the study was conducted was Cluster 4 of DepEd Davao City.

Davao City is geographically located in southeastern Mindanao, facing Davao Gulf and opposite the Island Garden City of Samal. The most significant city in terms of land area in the Philippines is Davao City, a first-class, highly urbanized city. Its entire area on land is 2,443.61 km². It has a tropical rainforest climate with 26 °F temperatures and 77 mm of rainfall on average each month. Demographically, it is the third most populous city in the Philippines, with 1.6 million residents growing at 2.3% annually, according to a census (PSA, 2015). Politically, it comprises three congressional districts and 11 administrative districts with 182 barangays (PSA, 2020). It is the primary trading center, center of commerce and industry, and industry hub of Mindanao. The city's industrial characterization is a highly service-oriented economy, industrial, agricultural, forestry, and fishing (PSA, 2018). Moreover, a significant size of the manufacturing sector of the Davao Region surrounds Davao City, according to the Nutrition Council of the Philippines, talking about food manufacturing (NCP, 2020).

Southeast of the Philippine island of Mindanao is where Davao City is situated. It is located close to the head of Davao Gulf at the Davao River's mouth. The city serves as the principal regional hub for southeast Mindanao, with its commercial area including about 50 minor ports.

Santa Ana, a small-vessel serving port located 5 miles (8 km) north, is protected by the Pakiputan Strait, formed by offshore Samal Island. The ports manage the transportation of copra, corn (maize), rice, and interisland passenger traffic. As a major international port, Davao City exports much abaca, the primary crop grown in the nearby agricultural hinterland. Abaca is a natural fiber.

The need for career self-management of public secondary school teachers in Davao City calls for urgent attention since it has been found out that most of the teachers are bachelor's degree holders, and only some proceed with graduate and professional school studies. Moreover, updates on personal and professional enhancement for teachers are minimal, and confirmation of this claim is necessary through this study.

Fig 2 Philippine Map and Davao City

➤ Population and Sample

Due to the size of the population, a stratified random selection method was utilized to choose study participants. The strata-based method was used in selecting people which was signified by percentage size in reaching a considerable sample for gathering the research data. Blay (2007) pointed out that in the stratified random sampling technique, the suited consideration is proportional allocation. He described stratified random sampling as a methodology for taking samples from populations that can be divided into smaller groups. He further explained that this involves splitting the large group into strata subgroups. Thus, this technique can ensure that the individuals in a population have an equal chance to participate in the study as a sample.

In addition, using raosoft.com, it directs a just number of samples due to an enormous population. Hence, the raosoft website is similar to Slovin's formula in calculating the total sample population of this study.

The study's respondents were the public secondary school teachers in Cluster 4 Division of Davao City for S.Y. 2020-2021. There were 555 secondary school teachers in the target cluster, and 228 teachers were the guaranteed samples following raosoft.com. The respondents were selected since the researcher resided on the respondents' target area, and the result generated can be utilized in understanding and evaluating teachers regarding their positive personality traits, self-efficacy, and career self-management.

Upon selecting the respondents, the researcher sets inclusion criteria to collect data entirely. These are as follows: secondary school teachers this school year 2020-2021 whose work stations are designated in Cluster 4 of the Davao City Division specifically, only those who were in public teaching service for at least three years. Otherwise, these exclusion criteria may be included: a teacher who does not work in Cluster 4 and those whose length of service was below three years. It is anticipated that no teachers withdrew in the middle of the study, and if there were any, an alternative respondent with the same qualification, especially gender and cluster belonging, was supposed to be replaced for voluntariness.

Based on the respondents' status quo, the researcher opts to study this phenomenon on a one-school-year basis. It is to ensure the accuracy of the gathered data within them.

➤ *Research Instrument*

This research study utilized three survey questionnaires assessing teachers' positive personality traits, self-efficacy, and career self-management. These questionnaires were adapted and modified by the researcher.

The Positive Personality Traits questionnaire was adapted from the study of Singh & Jha (2010). It has 43 items distributed 11 items for positive self-image, 11 for commitment, 11 for outward and people orientation, and ten for culture identification. Another survey questionnaire was also modified from the study of Heyne, Myerson, & Tonge (2014) for the instrument on teacher self-efficacy. It has 12 items distributed to academic and social stress with six items and separation and discipline stress with another six items.

- *In Describing the Positive Personality Traits, this was the used Five-Point Likert Scale:*

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	The positive personality traits of teachers are always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	High	The positive personality traits of teachers are often Manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The positive personality traits of teachers are sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	The positive personality traits of teachers are seldom manifested.
1.0 -1.79	Very Low	The positive personality traits of teachers are never Manifested.

- *In Describing the Teacher Self-Efficacy, the following Five-Point Likert Scale was used:*

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	The self-efficacy of teachers are always evident.
3.40 - 4.19	High	The self-efficacy of teachers are often evident.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The self-efficacy of teachers are sometimes evident.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	The self-efficacy of teachers are seldom evident.
1.0 -1.79	Very Low	The self-efficacy of teachers are not evident.

Another survey questionnaire for career self-management was adapted from the study of Runhaar et al. (2019), consisting of 13 items which were distributed to its indicators specified as five items for creating opportunities, four items for enhancing visibility, and four items for seeking advice.

- *In Describing the Teacher Self-Efficacy, the following Five-Point Likert Scale was used:*

Range of Means	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	The teachers always manifest career self-management.
3.40 - 4.19	High	The teachers often manifest career self-management.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderate	The teachers sometimes manifest career self-management.
1.80 - 2.59	Low	The teachers seldom manifest career self-management.
1.0 -1.79	Very Low	The teachers never manifest career self-management.

Content validity was secured by undergoing the validation process of all the survey questionnaires. First, the submission of research instruments to the research adviser was made to seek suggestions, comments, and recommendations for improvement' to finish this validation, copies were presented to a research panel of experts for instrument refinement. Within the last revision, the researcher incorporated the comments, suggestions, and corrections from the expert validators. As was done, validators consolidated the ratings and checked the status of the instruments. Secondly, the reliability index was observed by doing a pilot test on the same target respondents in another place. Lastly, to identify and test the items to be removed and revised, the data gathered underwent Cronbach Alpha; in this, the instruments addressed the level of comprehension within the target respondents.

➤ *Data Collection*

The following is the researcher's procedure for collecting the data from the research respondents.

The researcher primarily asked permission by sending a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent through the cluster head specifying the target area where the study was conducted. This was to make sure that prior to the study, the Department of Education Davao City Division was aware of the endeavor of the study, together with the involvement of respondents who were employed in the department.

After the Division's approval, the researcher sought permission from the school principals of Cluster IV to formally conduct the study. It was also attached in the letter with the approved response of the Division and their knowledge of administering survey questionnaires.

Since the approval of the School's Division Superintendent and school principals of Cluster IV was secured, another letter was made together with the informed consent, which was sent to the teacher respondents of the schools in Cluster IV. The letter also mentioned that the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal approved the study.

They ensured that the respondents were fully aware of the intention and their involvement in the study, which may they opt to join or otherwise voluntarily. Moreover, to be notified fully, the researcher sought responses from the respondents, whether positive or negative.

The researcher then sends the approved letter and the electronic copy of the instruments to the research respondents. And then administering the instruments to the teachers via Google form, stating that the moment they submitted the form was meant to allow the researcher to use the data for research purposes only.

After these procedures, the researcher downloaded the responses from the online survey via Google. This prepared the gathered data for tabulation, checking, and consolidation. The researcher then collected, checked, tabularized, and consolidated the results and immediately gave them to the statistician for data analysis.

Through this, the data gathered was analyzed and interpreted with the help of an expert in the field. The results were then depicted with implications after their analysis.

➤ *Statistical Tools*

In analyzing the data, these are the treats being maximized:

- *Weighted Mean.*

Its utilization was applied in determining the level of personality traits and career self-management of public secondary school teachers.

- *Pearson-r.*

Its utilization was applied in determining the significant relationship between personality traits and career-self management.

- *Regression Analysis.*

It was applied in determining the significant influence of personality traits towards career self-management and the domain in the personality traits that significantly influence attitude.

➤ *Ethical Consideration*

There are some empirical ethical issues and concerns influencing this study. Concerning issues were derived within the methodology involved in this study. The ethical disputes that applied to this research concern were also addressed. The concerns regarding conducting the study, confidentiality, and obscurity were considered.

The first issue was a request letter submitted to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent through the cluster head, securing permission to administer the study. After its approval, an approved letter was handed to either OIC's office or the principal of the schools where respondents have been working. By doing such, the researcher respects the personal viewpoint of the respondents in their participation in this study. The answered instruments were parched and sealed after data analysis and interpretation. Thus, the researcher followed ethical standards by acting upon the research protocol assessment criteria, most especially in handling the population and data collection.

- *Voluntary Participation.*

The public secondary school teachers of Cluster 4 of Davao City Division have the liberty to answer or not the instrument without any restrictions, especially mental consequences they may possibly discern. The researcher respects the personal viewpoint of the respondents in their participation in this study. Thus, after describing and presenting the study's purpose and benefits to the respondents, their rights in voluntary participation were considered and observed.

- *Privacy and Confidentiality.*

The respondent's identity required in the study was delt private, and the highest anonymity of the respondents' data was observed. The researcher fixated on essential ethical problems such as privacy, the viewpoint of the respondents, and veracity. Any failure to follow this guideline would mean positioning respondents' rights.

- *Recruitment.*

In recruitment, the students were purposively selected by indicating the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Furthermore, the data collection records, together with the process of questionnaire distribution among the respondents, were also emphasized. Lastly, in the data collection, the process of conducting the study was clearly stipulated.

- *Informed Consent Process.*

The research questionnaire was free of challenging terminologies. It was made with an understandable context for the respondents. It stated clear discussion profits to teaching and non-teaching personnel to generate after the study. Securing the support of the DepEd Davao Division authorities was prioritized before conducting and administering the research survey questionnaire. Therefore, given that authorities' approval was secured, the instrument was given to the public secondary school teachers of Cluster 4, DepEd Davao City.

- *Risks.*

The study ensured an intricate-free high-risk situation the respondents experienced regarding physical, psychological, or socio-economic concerns. The study focused on personality traits and the career self-management of public secondary school teachers in DepEd Davao City Cluster 4. The respondents intensified on rating the level of personality traits, self-efficacy, and the career self-management they manifest and their attributes.

- *Benefits.*

The result of the study was beneficial to the teachers, school administrator, and community in terms of getting criteria to a kind of personality traits and career self-management to synthesize the effective traits of teachers towards their tasks.

- *Plagiarism.*

The researcher ensured and observed the correct and accurate techniques in citing ideas from the expert authors or scholars. In doing so, this paper has undergone scholarly output assessment through Grammarly and Turnitin software.

- *Fabrication.*

Due to the existence of previous scholars, the researcher ensured that the tale was not made in the literature. Thus, all material shown was prudently written and cited. The sources utilized were steadfast journals, published research, and other scholarly works.

- *Falsification.*

This research fulfills the citation rules drawn in APA 6th edition format; henceforth, the study should have applied modifications and misinterpretations of work and data. The data presented are sought to be accurate.

- *Conflict of Interest.*

There was no trace of COI, wherein there was no set of conditions in which a professional judgment concerning primary interest, a secondary interest, such as monetary or academic advantages or recognitions, frequently influences a primary goal, such as the wellbeing of the participants or the veracity of the research.

- *Deceit.*

This study writes ups did not utilize any form of dishonesty to impair the respondents' welfare. A panel of experts thoroughly checked and assessed the content of the study for information validation.

- *Permission from Organization/Location.*

The research was conducted with reserved and particular obedience to ethical standards. Thus, a proper letter was sent to the DepEd Davao Division. The research is undertaken only after approval from the authorities.

- *Technological Issues.*

The use of Grammarly and Turnitin software was also observed in this study, considering that these two software programs have placed their credibility in the assurance of quality research output. Also, the use of Google Forms has been a part of public secondary school teachers' operational and functional duties. There are no technical concerns or problems due to technology use because public school teachers are used to this. Moreover, it has also been assured that respondents may contact the researcher for further assistance if they ever need assistance.

- *Authorship.*

Lastly, this study contemplates authorship credentials in the conduct of the study. The researcher significantly aided in the data collection, data analysis, and data interpretation processes. The important intellectual content was drafted and revised by the author and co-author critically. Both have contributed academically to reach the publication of the research study.

CHAPTER THREE RESULTS

This chapter presents the study's results based on the data gathered and analyzed.

➤ Level of Positive Personality Traits

Shown in Table 1 is the level of positive personality traits of secondary public secondary school teachers. It is depicted that the overall mean of *positive personality traits* of public secondary school teachers is *very high*, with a mean of 4.47 and a *very high standard deviation* of 0.35. As indicated, the teachers have a *very high level of commitment* based on the mean of 4.65 with a *very high standard deviation* of 0.36, followed by a *very high level of culture identification* based on its mean of 4.64 and a *very high standard deviation* of 0.42. Also, they have a *very high level of positive self-image*, with a mean of 4.47 and a *very high standard deviation* of 0.42. Lastly, they are at a *high level of outward and people orientation* based on the mean of 4.12 and a *high standard deviation* of 0.54.

Table 1 Level of Positive Personality Traits

Indicator	S.D.	Mean	Description
Positive Self-Image	0.42	4.47	Very High
Commitment	0.36	4.65	Very High
Outward and People Orientation	0.54	4.12	High
Culture Identification	0.42	4.64	Very High
Overall	0.35	4.47	Very High

➤ Level of Teacher Self-efficacy

Displayed in Table 2 is the overall mean of *teacher self-efficacy* of public secondary school teachers is 4.46, which means a *very high* and a *very high standard deviation* of 0.43. The two indicators were *very high: academic and social stress*, with a mean of 4.48 and a *standard deviation* of 0.46, and *separation discipline stress*, with a mean of 4.45 and a *standard deviation* of 0.46.

Table 2 Level of Teacher Self-efficacy

Indicator	S.D.	Mean	Description
Academic and Social Stress	0.46	4.48	Very High
Separation and Discipline Stress	0.46	4.45	Very High
Over-all	0.43	4.46	Very High

➤ Level of Career Self-Management

As revealed in Table 3, the *overall mean of career self-management* in public schools is 4.17, with a *high level* and a *high standard deviation* of 0.53. It is shown that the teachers have a *very high level of seeking advice* based on its mean of 4.37 and *very high standard deviation* of 0.61. Also, they have a *very high level of creating opportunities* based on a mean of 4.24 and a *standard deviation* of 0.52. Lastly, they are at a *high level of enhancing one's visibility* based on its mean of 3.91 and a *standard deviation* of 0.70.

Table 3 Level of Career Self-management

Indicator	S.D.	Mean	Description
Creating Opportunities	0.52	4.24	Very High
Enhancing One's Visibility	0.42	3.91	High
Seeking Advice	0.61	4.37	Very High
Over-all	0.53	4.17	High

➤ The Significant Relationship between Positive Personality Traits and Career Self-Management

As shown in Table 4 below, *positive personality traits* have a significant moderate positive correlation to *career self-management* from the rejection of the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance because of its *R-value* of 0.653; and *p-value* of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This means that career self-management can be attributed to positive personality traits. Correlating positive personality traits to the indicators of career self-management, it also has a significant relationship with creating opportunities with an *R-value* of 0.598, described as a moderate positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000. Likewise, it has a substantial connection to seeking advice with an *R-value* of 0.598, described as a moderate positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000. Lastly, it also has a significant relationship to enhancing visibility with an *R-value* of 0.494, described as a low positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000.

Taking by indicator, as an overall, *positive self-image* has a significant relationship to *career self-management* as it depicts an *R-value* of 0.496, described as a low positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000. *Positive self-image* has a significant relationship with *seeking advice*, with an *R-value* of 0.481, described as a low positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000.

It also has a significant relationship with *creating opportunities* with an *R-value* of 0.444, described as a low positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000. Lastly, *positive self-image* has a significant relationship with *enhancing visibility*, with an *R-value* of 0.359 described as a low positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000.

Commitment has a significant relationship to *career self-management* as it reveals an *R-value* of 0.437, which is described as a low positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000. To specify, *commitment* has a significant relationship with *seeking advice*. An *R-value* of 0.446 is described as a low positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000. Furthermore, it has a substantial connection with *creating opportunities* with an *R-value* of 0.382, described as a low positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000. Lastly, *commitment* has a significant relationship with *enhancing visibility* with an *R-value* of 0.303, described as a low positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000.

Outward and people orientation, based on an overall result, has a significant relationship to *career self-management* with an *R-value* of 0.585, described as a moderate positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000. It also has a significant relationship with *creating opportunities* with an *R-value* of 0.608, described as a moderate positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000. *Outward and people orientation* also have a significant relationship with *enhancing visibility* and *seeking advice*. The result showed that both indicators have an *R-value* of 0.466, a low positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000.

Cultural identification has a significant relationship to *career self-management* as it depicts with *R-value* of 0.541, described as a moderate positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000. It also has a significant relationship to *seeking advice*, with an *R-value* of 0.544, described as a moderate positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000, followed by a significant relationship to *enhancing visibility*, with an *R-value* of 0.417, described as a low positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000. Lastly, it has a significant relationship with *creating opportunities* with an *R-value* of 0.427, described as a low positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000.

Therefore, this result rejects the hypothesis of this study, stating there is no relationship between positive personality traits and career self-management.

Table 4 Significant Relationship between Positive Personality Traits and Career Self-Management

Positive Personality Traits	Career Self-Management			
	Creating opportunities	Enhancing One’s Visibility	Seeking Advice	Overall
Positive Self-Image	.444** (.000)	.359** (.000)	.481** (.000)	.496** (.000)
Commitment	.382** (.000)	.303** (.000)	.446** (.000)	.437** (.000)
Outward and People Orientation	.608** (.000)	.466** (.000)	.446** (.000)	.585** (.000)
Culture Identification	.427** (.000)	.417** (.000)	.544** (.000)	.541** (.000)
Overall	.598** (.000)	.494** (.000)	.598** (.000)	.653** (.000)

➤ *The Significant Relationship between Teacher Self-efficacy and Career Self-Management*

As shown in Table 5 below, *teacher self-efficacy* has a significant moderate positive correlation to *career self-management* from rejecting the hypothesis at a 0.05 significance level because of its *R-value* of 0.584; and *p-value* of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This means that *career self-management* can be attributed to *teacher self-efficacy*. Correlating *teacher self-efficacy* to the indicators of *career self-management* has a significant relationship to *seeking advice* with an *R-value* of 0.544, described as a moderate positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000. Furthermore, it shows a significant relationship to *creating opportunities* with an *R-value* of 0.541, a moderate positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000. Moreover, lastly, it also has a significant relationship to *enhancing visibility* with an *R-value* of 0.429, described as a low positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000.

As correlating the indicators of *teacher self-efficacy* to *career self-management*, on an overall basis, *academic and social stress* has a significant relationship to *career self-management* with an *R-value* of 0.606 described as a low positive correlation and *p-value* of 0.000. To specify, it was found that *academic and social stress* has a significant relationship with *seeking advice*, with an *R-value* of 0.569, described as a moderate positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000. Further, it is significantly related to *creating opportunities* with an *R-value* of 0.560, a moderate positive correlation, and a *p-value* of 0.000. Moreover, lastly, it also has a significant relationship to *enhancing visibility* with an *R-value* of 0.442, described as a low positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000.

In addition, based on the overall result, *separation and discipline stress* have a significant relationship to *career self-management*, with an *R-value* of 0.485, described as a moderate positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000. In every indicator, it is revealed that *separation and discipline stress* has a significant relationship with *creating opportunities*, with an *R-value* of 0.452, described as a low positive correlation and a *p-value* of 0.000. Moreover, it has a significant relationship to *seeking advice*

with an *R*-value of 0.447, described as a moderate positive correlation, and a *p*-value of 0.000. Lastly, it shows a significant relationship to *enhancing visibility* with an *R*-value of 0.359, a low positive correlation, and a *p*-value of 0.000.

Therefore, this result rejects the study's hypothesis, stating that no significant relationship exists between teacher self-efficacy and career self-management.

Table 5 Significant Relationship between Teacher Self-Efficacy and Career Self-Management

Teacher Self-Efficacy	Career Self-Management			
	Creating opportunities	Enhancing One's Visibility	Seeking Advice	Overall
Academic and Social Stress	.560** (.000)	.442** (.000)	.569** (.000)	.606** (.000)
Separation and Discipline Stress	.452** (.000)	.359** (.000)	.447** (.000)	.485** (.000)
Overall	.541** (.000)	.429** (.000)	.544** (.000)	.584** (.000)

➤ *The Significant Influence of Positive Personality Traits on Career Self-management*

As shown in the table below, the indicators, with a *positive self-image, outward and people orientation, and cultural identification*, significantly influence career self-management as it shows less than the *p*-value of 0.05. However, only the commitment indicator of positive personality traits does not significantly influence career self-management as it is more significant than the 0.05 *p*-value.

As can be seen, *positive personality traits* significantly influence *career self-management*. Moreover, the standardized regression coefficients show that *positive self-image, outward and people orientation, and cultural identification* are strong predictors than *commitment*.

Further, only the *positive self-image, outward and people orientation, and cultural identification* significantly influence *career self-management*, evident with the *p*-value at 0.05 significance level. Thus, the total attribution of career self-management is only 0.455 to positive personality traits.

Table 6 The Significant Influence of Positive Personality Traits on Career Self-management

Positive Personality Traits	Career Self-Management			
	B	Beta	t-value	p-value
Positive Self-Image	.199	.159	2.366	.019
Commitment,	-.016	-.011	-.156	.876
Outward and People Orientation	.365	.377	6.321	.000
Culture Identification	.371	.297	4.612	.000
R ²	.455			
F-value	46.560			
P-value	.000			

$\alpha = 0.05$

➤ *Significant Influence of Teacher Self-efficacy on Career Self-management*

The table below shows that *academic and social stress* significantly influences *career self-management*, showing less than 0.05 of its *p*-value. In contrast, *separation and discipline stress* do not significantly influence career self-management as it shows a greater than 0.05 *p*-value.

Teacher *self-efficacy* significantly influences *career self-management* as it shows less than a 0.05 *p*-value. Moreover, it displays that *academic and social stress* is a strong predictor than *separation and discipline stress*. Further, only *academic and social stress* significantly influence *career self-management*, as evidenced by a 0.05 level of significance, making it to the conclusion that the hypothesis is rejected. Thus only 0.369 of the career self-management can be attributed to teacher self-efficacy.

Table 7 Significant Influence of Teacher Self-efficacy on Career Self-management

Variable	Multiple Regression Weight		t-value	p-value
	B	B		
Academic and Social Stress	0.632	0.549	6.931	0.000
Separation and Discipline Stress	0.088	0.076	0.959	0.338
R ²	0.369			
F-value	65.882			

P-value	.000			
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$\alpha = 0.05$

➤ *Combined Influence of Positive Personality Traits and Teacher Self-efficacy on Career Self-management*

The table below shows that *positive personality traits and teacher self-efficacy* are highly significant to *career self-management* when combined, as it shows a *p-value < 0.05*. Furthermore, the standardized regression coefficients show that positive personality traits and teacher self-efficacy strongly influenced career self-management. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected, stating that there is no significant influence between positive personality traits and teacher self-efficacy, both in individual and aggregate capacity. It shows the 0.458 attributions of career self-management to positive personality traits and teacher self-efficacy.

Table 8 Combined Influence of Positive Personality Traits and Teacher Self-efficacy on Career Self-management

Variable	Multiple Regression Weight		t-value	p-value
	B	B		
Positive Personality Traits	0.726	0.480	6.961	0.000
Teacher Self-efficacy	0.305	0.247	0.3591	0.000
R ²	0.458			
F-value	94.910			
P-value	.000			

$\alpha = 0.05$

CHAPTER FOUR DISCUSSION

The chapter tackles a discussion of the results, conclusion, and recommendation.

➤ *Level of Positive Personality Traits*

It is shown in the result that the positive personality trait of public secondary school teachers is at a very high level. This implies that the positive personality traits of teachers are always manifested, as described in the interpretation scale of this study. Moreover, the result reveals that Khalilzadeh and Khodi's (2018) claim regarding personality traits within deciding on your career management is supported by this study. It is claimed that personality trait is a prominent factor in a successful career choice, especially when combined with motivation.

Furthermore, it is shown in the result that secondary public secondary school teachers have a very high level of commitment. It implies that this indicator of the positive personality trait of teachers is always manifested among them. Seeing this means that they are committed to their teaching career as a whole, as Cox (2017) stipulated. Moreover, they bided by the rules and regulations in embracing the principles of the teaching profession, as well as the requirements. However, it debunks the claim of Shirbagi (2007), revealing that public secondary school teachers have risks and the probability of resigning and deviating towards another profession.

Additionally, it is displayed in the results that secondary public secondary school teachers have a very high level of cultural identification. It implies that this indicator of the positive personality trait of teachers is always manifested. This study is supported by Singh & Jha (2010), revealing that teachers, in this case, have a high culture orientation. This comprises knowledge of one's traditions, patriotism, and tolerance towards others. Moreover, it is reinforced by the claim of Chen (2014) stating that secondary public secondary school teachers have an identification or sense of belongingness based on various cultural categories, including nationality, race, ethnicity, gender, and religion. More likely, as their result shows exceptionally high, it is found that the process of sharing collective knowledge such as traditions, heritage, language, aesthetics, norms, and customs are constructed and maintained.

It is shown in the result that public school teachers have a very high level of positive self-image, which means that this indicator of the positive personality trait of teachers is always manifested. Moreover, they have an affirmative orientation toward maintaining a positive self-image. This includes seeing the self optimistically, flexible, emotionally intelligent, just, spiritual, trustworthy, and self-reliant. The result implies that the idea of Lynch (2020), who stated that acquiring positive self-image could boost a person physically, mentally, socially, emotionally, and spiritually, wherein it is applicable and connected to the result of the study. Thus, it affirms the study of Mehrkish & Grant (2021), implying that a positive self-image strongly impacts their performance in their designated workstation.

Lastly, the result displays that the teachers have a high level of outward and people orientation. It implies that this indicator of positive personality traits of teachers is often manifested. This depicts that teachers have confidence in themselves. The study of Singh & Jha (2010) supports this research result by clearly pointing out that teachers can be outgoing and gregarious in social situations in a zestful approach, wherein they show self-esteem and confidence to lead others. These public secondary school teachers can always mix with others easily with people close to them, have an exciting life, and have made decisions that lead to success. While they are often turned to by people who need direction when there is a leading officer, people often turn to them for advice. Furthermore, it supports the idea that these teachers can perform well in people and task orientation (Gartzia & Baniandres, 2016).

➤ *Level of Teacher Self-efficacy*

As a result, public school teachers have a very high level of teacher self-efficacy. This implies that the self-efficacy of teachers is always evident.

Also, it shows that they had strong self-confidence in their capacity to handle the duties, responsibilities, and difficulties associated with their line of work, which act as an influential factor in academic outcomes and the working environment by Van Acker et al. (2013) in Shu (2022). By this, the notion of Bandura, 1997 in Heyne, Myerson, & Tonge (2014) supports the result of this study by emphasizing that due to the coping behavior, there are real response expectations within a person's self-efficacy. Thus, this includes effort together with a degree of persistence in the face of difficulties. It is also shown that they have very high academic and social stress levels. This implies that this indicator within the self-efficacy of teachers is always evident.

Public teachers can do tasks described in the job description. Also, they can approach their co-workers about something; and handles questions harmoniously with one another. Further, they can do tasks and other related matters before their co-workers. Moreover, this depicts that they can stand up for themselves whenever they experience being teased or bullied. This result recounts the claim of Nyambongi (2013) that the achievement of high levels is reliably associated with a range of causal factors which may include but are not limited to intrinsic motivation to teach, individual vulnerability, and systematic influences.

The participants also have a very high separation and discipline stress indicator. This implies that this indicator within the self-efficacy of teachers is always evident. It depicts that they can cope with being away from family during school. Further, they can independently stay away from home for school activities.

Additionally, they can handle being growled, punished, or conferenced by authorities due to their actions. With this result, it can be implied that public school teachers can cope in emotionally challenging situations due to a threat to their security or a threat of conference or punishment by authorities. Thus, this result is connected to the study of Heyne, Myerson, & Tonge (2014), that their high level of separation and discipline stress implies a lower risk of separation anxiety or fear of retribution.

➤ *Level of Career Self-management*

It is shown in the result that public school teachers have a high level of career self-management. It can be interpreted that the teachers often manifest career self-management, as indicated in the interpretation description. It depicts that they have a great manifestation in managing their career for improvement and addressing needs and difficulties, creating opportunities, enhancing their visibility, and seeking advice. Moreover, it supports the study of Marcinek (2015), which states that they know the available options because they determine what they want and are capable of. Furthermore, this could be based on their competence and ambitions as a teacher. It was seen that it could improve insights in managing career leading to satisfaction of career, as King (2014) corroborates his study towards this research result. Additionally, it connects to the claim of Jacowski (2021) that manifesting a high level of career self-management comprised of continuously improving the existent conditions at the present workplace and preparing yourself for a change.

It is shown in the result that teachers have a very high level of seeking advice. This implies that teachers always manifest this indicator of career self-management. It depicts that these teachers always ask experienced colleagues for assistance related to their career development. Further, they always have a network of colleagues within the school who assists them with their specialized progress. Also, they always believe that discussing target goals with colleagues manifests professional and career development. Lastly, they always ask colleagues from outside my department for guidance related to my professional and trade development. This result supports the idea of Rijt, Boscche, Van De Wiel, & Maeyer (2013), who stated that this indicator is considered an essential step in problem-solving and learning in organizations. Also, it was claimed to have a higher chance of probability that teachers seek help upward for the betterment of their service in their career development. As the study of Berebitsky and Andrews-Larson (2017) validates this study result by connecting the context that teachers' relationship with superiors and other teachers who have implications for the betterment of the instructional practice of co-teachers because their influence and guidance would be of great help towards the latter.

It is also shown in the result that these public secondary school teachers have a very high level of creating opportunities. This reveals that they always manifest this indicator of career self-management as stipulated in the interpretation describing the result of the data. Moreover, it implies that teachers can initiate independently to generate prospects. These public secondary school teachers often create activities that their colleagues need to give more attention to and usually try to get in touch with influential people around their job vicinity. Also, these teachers invest in a network of colleagues who keep them informed about developments in the school. They also ensure that they develop relevant skills and knowledge necessary in managing a classroom or school and develop competencies that allow them to achieve their goals. Thus, this result supports the study of Marcinek (2015), which also found that creating opportunities can be seen by teachers who open doors in initiation activities on themes commonly ignored by others.

Lastly, in enhancing one's visibility, it is shown in the result that teachers got a high level. This means that the teachers often manifest this indicator of career self-management as explained in the interpretation of the description level given in the instrument. Further, it shows that these public secondary school teachers often share with their supervisors their dreams, they often tell their supervisor which tasks they prefer, they often make sure their superior is aware of their performance, and they often ask their supervisor for advice related to their professional- and career development. This study outcome supports the claim of Runhaar, Bouwmans, & Vermeulen (2019) that this career self-management is visible when the teachers can inform their supervisors when they achieve success. Thus, their openness toward their supervisors can enhance their visibility. Moreover, it also affirms the study of Tuitt (2010) that it develops engagement in teachers' senses because it develops their ideas without compromising their dignity and humanity.

➤ *Significant Relationship between Positive Personality Traits and Career Self-management*

It is shown in the result that positive personality traits and career self-management have a significant moderate positive correlation. Thus, it rejects the hypothesis of this study regarding the relationship between positive personality traits and career self-management. Correlating positive personality traits to the indicators of career self-management, all the hands, to wit: creating opportunities, enhancing visibility, and seeking advice, reveals a significant moderate positive correlation. Most notably, all the indicators of positive personality traits have a significant relationship to the hands of career self-management, which are creating opportunities, enhancing visibility, and seeking advice.

Revealing this result highly supports the study of Alkheilil (2016), which claims that personality influences the career management of every individual due to the person's driving force or career self-management. Although individuals may vary in their personal preferences, their attitude toward work helps them develop their career self-management. Moreover, this also backs up the proposition of the study of Lin, Luan, Zhao, et al. (2022), who testifies that personality traits and career self-management have emerged as significantly related to each other because personality traits are associated with a broad range of career belief and performance variables and irrespective of occupation. To elaborate further, teachers are viewed as the primary actors in steering their careers, which means they are aware and knowledgeable of the consequences of their actions as they do their tasks at work. Thus, as Runhaar, Bouwmans, & Vermeulen (2019) supported this result of the study, they affirm scholarly research studies are illuminating that there is an increase of attribution on the accountability of handling one's career to teachers' personality traits. However, this research study result debunks the study of Kemboi, R.J.K., Kindiki, N., and Misigo, N. (2016), who stipulated that personality does not predict career self-management of an individual also reject the claim that there are personality traits that do not relate to career self-management.

➤ *Significant Relationship between Teacher Self-efficacy and Career Self-management*

It is shown in the result that teacher self-efficacy has a significantly moderate positive correlation to career self-management. Thus, it rejects the hypothesis of this study regarding the relationship between self-efficacy and career self-management. Correlating teacher self-efficacy to the indicators of career self-management, all the indicators, to wit: creating opportunities, enhancing visibility, and seeking advice. Most notably, all the hands of teacher self-efficacy, with academic and social stress and separation and discipline stress, have a significant relationship to the indicators of career self-management, which are creating opportunities, enhancing visibility, and seeking advice. Thus, this result rejects the hypothesis stated in this study.

The result of this study supports Reddan's (2015) study course, where he found out that teacher self-efficacy and career self-management have a significant relationship. As it is incorporated in his study, it authenticates that teachers' awareness of their strengths and weaknesses in their self-efficacy and career self-management, they have a broader understanding of how they could attain goals and plan in their careers. Moreover, this also reinforced the claim of Sun (2019) claim that teachers' career management is highly related to their awareness of their match within their load or self-efficacy, as he concludes that when a teacher lacks self-efficacy, they are less likely to have the confidence to make appropriate decisions for their career self-management. Aside from these, this also affirms the study findings of Alisic and Wiese (2020), who revealed that self-efficacy and career self-management are significantly corrected, implying that these variables have a significant relationship.

They concluded that when teachers decrease their career insecurity, self-efficacy increases, enhancing career self-management. Further explanation shows that teachers built the responsibility of managing their careers as they have high self-efficacy. Thus, the more efficient teachers are, the more they can work themselves.

Additionally, it supports research from South Korea that asserts any obstacles encountered have a high correlation with career self-efficacy since emotions and self-confidence are key factors in career decision-making.

Their study shows that the career self-efficacy behavior a person has, the higher level of career management and decision-making he will commit. Thus, it implies that since self-efficacy is related to career preparation behavior, it specifies that career self-efficacy directly affects it. Lastly, it related to the study findings of Makki, Feng, Waqar, & Adhikari (2023), who concluded that a firm conviction in one's abilities and capabilities would affect a person's decision-making in career exploration management.

➤ *Significant Influence of Positive Personality Traits on Career Self-management*

Among the domains of positive personality traits, only the commitment indicator does not significantly influence career self-management. On the other hand, positive self-image, outward and people orientation, and cultural identification significantly influence career self-management. Positive personality traits significantly influence the career self-management of public secondary school teachers. However, only half of the percentage of career self-management can be attributed to positive personality traits.

Personality significantly impacts how motivated people are to choose a potential vocation and how they manage that profession. Conscientiousness, openness to experience, and extraversion are personality traits that are positively correlated with intrinsic reasons for selecting a career in teaching and negatively correlated with extrinsic motivation and backup options, according to empirical data. Moreover, in the study of Tomsik & Gatial (2018), in the field of education, private or public institutions, it is evidently confirmed that personality traits positively correlate with choosing a teaching career path as a profession. Individuals bring some differences to work. Moreover, Lin, Luan, Zhao, et al. (2022) found that personality traits have direct and moderating effects on career decisiveness and its antecedents. In addition, personality's influence on career decisiveness is significant.

Lastly, personality associates fundamental choices in life, including life partner, profession, and career. As it corroborates the study of Makki, Feng, Waqar, & Adhikari (2023), putting into contextualization that suitability is the priority of teachers' desire, especially in making career jobs and work trades. Career implies social identity. A career heightens self-esteem and a sense of belongingness and establishes relationships among community members. By this, a career is essential to all.

➤ *Significant Influence of Teacher Self-efficacy on Career Self-management*

Teacher positivity significantly influences career self-management, while instructional practices do not significantly influence career self-management. Thus, this explicitly depicts that teachers' self-efficacy significantly affects career self-management.

This study supports the study of Kaushal and Vashisht (2021), which shows that with the use of moderating effect, which is the proactive personality, they have tested a model of self-efficacy and career self-management. As part of standing firm with the claim of Rahim, Jafar, and Arsad (2021), even way before the convergence of mentality, it can firmly confirm that a person's efficacy has a profound influence on their self-management whether it is in career or work, and even lifestyle. Furthermore, it backs up the experimental research of Reddin which concluded that self-efficacy influences career management after it was proven authentic by the gathered and interpreted data after experimentation. Also, the proposition of Lent, Ireland, Penn, Morris, and Sappington (2017) is that self-efficacy is relative to career exploration and decision-making activities, which eventually leads to career self-management.

➤ *Combined Influence of Positive Personality Traits and Teacher Self-efficacy on Career Self-management*

Positive personality traits and teacher self-efficacy significantly influence career self-management when combined.

Lin, Luan, Zhao, et al. (2022) state that personality traits and self-efficacy have emerged as significant determinants in life, like career and job-related outcomes. Independent of occupation and nationality, it is presumable that personality traits and other factors are linked to a wide range of career beliefs and performance metrics. The fields of personality and self-efficacy are linked not only through standard methodology and conceptual propositions but also through applying most occupational models, implying that career development is an extension of personality.

While Kaushal & Vashisht (2021) explained that personality and efficacy through occupational readiness and self-development feedback seeking, it significantly associates career self-management behaviors.

CHAPTER FIVE CONCLUSION

➤ *In Light of the Study, the following Conclusions were Drawn:*

The level of positive personality traits of public secondary school teachers is very high. Their positive self-image, commitment, and cultural identification are also very high. However, their outward and people orientation is only at a high level. This means that they always manifest positive personality traits in general. Among all the indicators, public secondary school teachers often manifest only the outward and people orientation.

The level of teacher self-efficacy of public secondary school teachers is very high. Their academic and social stress and separation and discipline stress are also very high. This means that the teachers' self-efficacy is always evident. It also concludes that self-efficacy indicators are always apparent among public secondary school teachers.

The career self-management of public secondary school teachers is at a high level. Their creating opportunities and seeking advice is at a very high level. However, enhancing one's visibility is at a high level. This means that teachers always manifest career self-management. However, only enhancing one's visibility is often displayed by them.

The relationship between positive personality traits and career self-management is significantly positive and moderately correlated. Also, all the indicators of positive personality traits are significantly related to all indicators of career self-management. This means that positive personality traits relate to the career self-management of public secondary school teachers. This indicates that the career self-management of teachers is affected by their positive personality traits. Thus, the hypothesis is rejected.

Further, the relationship between a teacher's self-efficacy and career is significantly moderately positive. Also, the indicators of teacher's self-efficacy: academic and social stress, separation, and discipline stress, has significantly moderate positive correlates with the indicators of career self-management as creating opportunity and seeking advice. However, a teacher's self-efficacy indicator has a significantly low positive correlation to enhancing one's visibility. This means a teacher's self-efficacy has a moderate positive relationship with career self-management. It indicates that career self-management is moderately affected by the teacher's self-efficacy. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected.

Teachers' positive personality traits significantly influence career self-management, especially positive self-image, outward and people orientation, and cultural identification. However, commitment does not significantly influence career management. This indicates that positive personality traits affect the career self-management of teachers.

Moreover, there is a significant influence of teacher self-efficacy on career self-management. The indicator separation and discipline stress do not significantly influence career self-management. However, academic and social stress does.

Lastly, positive personality traits and teacher self-efficacy are highly significant to career self-management. Thus, this indicates the hypothesis is rejected, which states that there is no significant influence between positive personality traits and teacher self-efficacy, both in individual and aggregate capacity.

RECOMMENDATION

➤ *Based on the Result of the Study, the following Recommendations were Formulated:*

Since public secondary school teachers have very high levels of positive personality traits, it is recommended that teachers maintain the characteristics they are used to for any possible development they may opt to indulge in. Also, school administrators or principals may sustain their practices toward their teachers.

Since public school teachers have a very high level of self-efficacy, it is recommended that teachers create initiatives through a form of symposium or any related activity which helps other professionals sustain self-efficacy. Also, school administrators or principals may support the endeavors of teachers by granting permission for their growth.

Since public school teachers have a high level of career self-management, it is recommended that teachers pursue their envisioned career path by working out for their position reclassification. Also, school administrators or principals may assist the teachers' career management through guides associated with the DepEd memorandums.

Since positive personality traits and career self-management have a significant relationship, public school teachers may develop seminars and symposiums that would assist other professions in topics related to this boosting and maintaining their positive personality traits and career self-management.

Since teachers' self-efficacy and career self-management has a significant relationship, it can be suggested that teachers may preserve their motivations, positivity, and instructional practices, which leads them to be an efficient individual within their profession by checking on their productivity with the goals or task given to them.

Since positive personality trait has a significant influence on career self-management, teachers may continue to characterize their established peculiarity to achieve goals related to their career management by doing a self-assessment checklist.

Since self-efficacy significantly influences career self-management, it can be recommended that teachers may opt to enact professional activities that would increase their public relations with other people for a good rapport within their manifested career management.

Since positive personality traits and teacher self-efficacy significantly influence career management, public school teachers are also recommended to maintain their positive personality traits, teacher self-efficacy, and career self-management by engaging in meaningful activities relating to these perceptions. The school administrator and school leaders are suggested to track the teachers in monitoring and addressing some concerns regarding their positive personality traits, teacher self-efficacy, and career self-management. Further research on the correlation between positive personality traits, teacher self-efficacy, and career self-management on the association of other spheres is suggested for further enrichment. Expansion of these variables is also recommended qualitatively to get in-depth details. This study is suggested for replication using other frameworks and scopes on the positive confirmation and further elaboration of the known information.

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